

marker #9A

0.02

marker #13A

0.02

marker #41

0.005

marker #44

0.004

marker #45_p2

0.003

marker #46

0.003

marker #50

0.004

marker #51_1 (three sequences subtended by a long branch removed)

0.004

marker #52

0.005

marker #54_p1

0.003

marker #56

0.003

marker #57

0.006

marker #58

0.005

marker #63

0.004

0.002

0.004